

Systemic Discrimination and Racism in the School and Workforce Pathways of Youth with Refugee Experience in Nova Scotia

Ifeyinwa Mbakogu¹, Chana Tikvah Wielinga¹, Lotanna Odiyi¹

¹Dalhousie University, Canada

Abstract

Although Nova Scotia (NS) has prioritized attracting and retaining newcomers from around the world, there is a paucity of research on the experiences of refugees in the province. In particular, is the minimal research on youth with refugee experience (YRE), considering that approximately half of all refugees are 18 years of age and younger. This paper addresses this gap by presenting findings from research that examines the pre-departure and arrival experiences of 21 youth with refugee experience in Nova Scotia. The paper examines the impact of racism on the resettlement of YREs by presenting the voices and experiential contributions of participants within the enabling framework of critical race theory (CRT). The narratives show that despite fostering a reputation as one of the most welcoming destinations for newcomers, youth with refugee experience often face systemic discrimination and racism, particularly in seeking employment and within educational institutions. The findings provide better understanding of the experiences of YRE, with accessing services and meeting their long-term economic goals that the provincial government, service providers, and researchers may apply to improve the pathways for YRE as they pursue employment in Nova Scotia.

Keywords: Racism, refugee youth, nova scotia, systemic discrimination, employment, education.

INTRODUCTION

In 2001, 4.6% of Nova Scotia's population, or 41,175 people, were immigrants (Statistics Canada, 2017). By 2016, that number had increased to 6.1 %, or 55,675 people (Statistics Canada, 2017). In 2021, Nova Scotia had a record-breaking 9,020 new permanent residents (Labour, Skills, and Immigration, 2022). Currently, Nova Scotia aims to attract 25,000 newcomers per year by 2060 (Labour, Skills, and Immigration, 2022). The number of refugees arriving in Nova Scotia is also increasing. Between 2005 and 2010, there were 1,176 new refugee permanent residents in Nova Scotia (Citizenship and Immigration Canada, 2014). In contrast, between 2011 and 2016, that number increased to 1,975 - about 16.8% of the newcomers (Statistics Canada, 2017).

Within Canada's Refugee and Humanitarian Resettlement Programme (RHRP), there are three categories of refugee sponsorship: Government-Assisted Refugees (GAR), Privately Sponsored Refugees (PSR), and Blended Visa Office-Referred (BVOR) Refugees (IRCC, 2016). GARs are sponsored and supported solely by the Canadian government, which provides initial services and income support for up to one year (IRCC, 2016). GARs are often referred by the United Nations Refugee Agency (UNHCR) or other designated referral agencies (IRCC, 2016). Due to the *Immigration and Refugee Protection Act* (IRPA), GARs are selected based on their need for protection, and those within this group may have higher needs than other refugee groups (IRCC, 2016). PSRs, on the other hand, may be sponsored by permanent residents, Canadian citizens, or private organisations rather than the government (IRCC, 2016). These sponsors provide financial support for up to one year after resettlement (IRCC, 2016); however, PSRs still have access to some government-based resettlement services (Wilkinson & Garcea, 2017). Finally, BVOR refugees are referred by the UNHCR or other designated referral agencies and selected by Canadian visa officers, who post their profiles on websites for potential sponsors to review (IRCC, 2016). BVOR refugees receive six months of income support from the government and six months from private sponsors. Since BVOR refugees are not eligible for government-based resettlement services, their private sponsors are responsible for emotional and social support (IRCC, 2016). However, there can be differences in the

Corresponding Author

Ifeyinwa Mbakogu, School of Social Work,
Dalhousie University, Canada
E-mail: ifeyinwa.mbakogu@dal.ca

Received : 13 July 2025

Accepted : 22 October 2025

Online Published : 22 December 2025

2025 JSER, Available online at
<https://www.journalser.com>

Cite this article as: Mbakogu, I., Wielinga C. T., Odiyi, L. (2025). Systemic discrimination and racism in the school and workforce pathways of youth with refugee experience in Nova Scotia. *Journal of Social and Educational Research*, 4(2), 139-148. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17868439>

resettlement experiences of GARs, PSRs, and BVOR refugees (Kaida et al., 2019; Senthanaar et al., 2020). For instance, some studies suggest that PSRs experience quicker and easier integration than GARs. Kaida et al. (2019) attribute this to differences in location, as PSRs tend to reside in major urban centres such as Vancouver, Toronto, and Montreal, which offer more employment opportunities. In contrast, Senthanaar et al. (2020) highlight differences between educational qualifications and skill sets, as GARs tend to be selected based on their vulnerability rather than their educational and work backgrounds. PSRs may have better career and integration prospects based on their existing language skills and qualifications (IRCC, 2016). Nevertheless, research has shown that all newcomers face significant challenges in the Canadian labour market regarding the devaluation of their non-Canadian education and work experiences (Cornelissen & Turcotte, 2020; Moffit et al., 2020; Picot et al., 2007; Sakamoto et al., 2010). This devaluation particularly impacts racialised newcomers (Akkaymak, 2017; Block et al., 2019; Grenier & Xue, 2011; Suto, 2009). Wilkinson and Garcea (2017) explain that newcomers can often only access menial jobs for which they are overqualified during their first five years of their residency in Canada.

Although all newcomers must demonstrate immense resilience throughout their resettlement journeys, some researchers report that refugees tend to experience additional challenges, especially in finding work that is commensurate with their skill level (Desiderio, 2016; Senthanaar et al., 2020), while Nourpanah (2014) critiques the portrayal of refugees as victims who require saving. Bearing their agency in mind, this paper begins by highlighting the paucity of research on youth with refugee experience (YRE) that explores the impact of racism and discrimination on their resettlement in Canada. The paper also presents our findings on the impact of racism on the resettlement of YRE in Nova Scotia by situating their voices and experiential contributions within the enabling framework of Critical Race Theory (CRT). The findings will provide a better understanding of the experiences of YRE while accessing services in Nova Scotia, insights that provincial policymakers, service providers, and researchers can apply to improve pathways for youth as they pursue employment.

Critical race theory

At its core, Critical Race Theory (CRT) critiques and challenges the liberal ideologies around which Western society is structured, including claims of objectivity, neutrality, and colour-blindness of the law (Abrams & Moio, 2009), as well as equality theory, enlightenment rationalism, and legal reasoning (Delgado & Stefancic, 2017).

Over time, CRT has been applied to multiple disciplines (Abrams & Moio, 2009). Additionally, CRT is a broad field with diverse contributors and subdivisions. For instance, Delgado and Stefancic (2017) present six basic tenets (including racism, interest convergence, race as a social construction, and differential racialisation) for engaging in a theoretical analysis. They view *racism* as endemic, with racism permeating society's structures and practices, remaining unacknowledged and 'invisible' to those who hold racial

privilege (Abrams & Moio, 2009) while simultaneously being an everyday experience for racialised people (Delgado & Stefancic, 2017). Delgado and Stefancic's (2017) inclusion of *interest convergence, or materialist determinism*, recognises that dominant racial groups, particularly White elites, and working-class Whites, profit materially and psychologically from racism and therefore, have little motivation to address it. Thus, as Bell (1997) adds, progressive change only occurs if it benefits White people. With their third tenet, CRT views *race as a social construction* with no basis in biology or genetics. Races are socially constructed categories that are invented, manipulated, and even retired when convenient (Delgado & Stefancic, 2017). However, CRT also recognises that these social categories significantly affect people's lives (Abrams & Moio, 2009). Their fourth tenet, *differential racialisation*, acknowledges that the dominant society racialises groups of people differently at different times, depending on historical, social, and economic contexts, particularly in the labour market (Delgado & Stefancic, 2017). It is critical to examine how race connects with other identities and forms of oppression, as a one-dimensional analysis can perpetuate the exclusionary patterns that CRT seeks to address (Abrams & Moio, 2009). By incorporating the fifth tenet, *intersectionality, and anti-essentialism*, CRT recognises that all people possess multiple, intersecting identities that simultaneously impact their experiences (Delgado & Stefancic, 2017). Delgado and Stefancic's (2017) final tenet, *the inclusion of voices of colour*, reinforces the view that people of colour possess a deeper knowledge and understanding of their experiences with race and racism (Delgado & Stefancic, 2017) than those from the dominant group.

The paper applies CRT based on its recognition that dominant historical narratives have been constructed to exclude the voices and lived realities of racialised people (Abrams & Moio, 2009), particularly those of racialised youth with refugee experience. Our paper emphasises that CRT values the stories and narratives of racialised youths with refugee experience who are commonly excluded from dominant academic knowledge and supports their use as a theoretical analysis tool (Schroeter & James, 2015).

The paucity of Research on refugee youth's experiences with racism in Nova Scotia

One of the primary challenges that refugees face in Canada is racism (Guo-Brennan & Guo-Brennan, 2019; Pelley, 2022). However, there is a lack of research focused on the experiences of refugee youth with racism in the province (Beagan et al., 2011; Etowa et al., 2016; Hamilton-Hinch, 2015; Bernard, 2020; Waldron, 2018). As such, we extended our literature search to include the experiences of YREs with racism in the Maritimes (Baker, 2021); newcomers in the Maritimes (Abidi et al., 2013; Allain et al., 2020; Pottie-Sherman & Graham, 2021); newcomer youth in Canada (Msofe, 2021; Guo-Brennan & Guo-Brennan, 2019); and newcomers in Canada, with a specific focus on employment (Edge & Newbold, 2013; Akkaymak, 2017; Grenier & Xue, 2011; Cornelissen & Turcotte, 2020; Block et al., 2019; Suto, 2009; Moffit et al., 2020; Kaida et al., 2019; Senthanaar et al., 2020).

Baker's (2021) survey of high school-attending refugee youth in Newfoundland and Labrador found that all of them had experienced racism, with adverse effects on their lives. Racism created an unwelcoming environment for these YREs and caused undue stress, with devastating impacts, particularly when students had to share their experiences with individuals who doubted their narratives (Baker, 2021). In general, Baker (2021) found that YREs were experiencing increased instances of overt, peer-driven racism in St. John's. Similar findings have been reported in other locations in Canada. For instance, Guo et al. (2019) found that GAR children from Syria experienced significant racist bullying in public schools in Alberta, which left the children feeling sad, angry, and hurt; prevented them from developing a sense of belonging and connection; and threatened their sense of religious and cultural identity. Moreover, when the children attempted to address these experiences, teachers often responded in discriminatory and dismissive ways (Guo et al., 2019). In many cases, the teachers demonstrated a lack of understanding of the lived realities of refugees (Guo et al., 2019). Furthermore, teachers' reactions to reported cases by affected children were sometimes influenced by stereotypical notions of refugees as unruly or violent.

Different experiences for white and racialized refugees

In the wake of the Russian invasion of Ukraine in February 2022, dominant Western responses have illustrated the depth of racism that exists within European and North American societies. Media coverage has been dominated by comparisons of the primarily White, European refugees to Black and Brown refugees from the Middle East, South America, and Africa (McCloskey, 2022). For instance, Philippe Corbe with France's BFM-TV said, "We're not talking here about Syrians fleeing the bombing of the Syrian regime backed by Putin. We're talking about Europeans leaving in cars that look like ours to save their lives" (McCloskey, 2022, pp. 139-140). Such statements utilize negative, racist stereotypes and ideologies about the Middle East and Africa to stimulate empathy for Ukraine. In doing so, the media reinforces existing racist narratives that present nations within the Global North as progressive and civilized while depicting nations in the Global South as violent and uncivilized. These narratives, in turn, portray racialized refugees as inherently less deserving of solidarity and support than White refugees (McCloskey, 2022).

Beyond media coverage, government responses to Ukrainian refugees contrast sharply with those toward previous refugee groups. One drastic example is Poland, which has welcomed more than 2.5 million Ukrainian refugees, even stating that asylum seekers do not require valid passports. However, in November 2021, Poland deployed 20,000 border police equipped with water cannons and tear gas to repel refugees from the Middle East (McCloskey, 2022). Although perhaps less dramatic, the response by the Canadian government also reveals the systemic racism that exists in the country. Canada has pledged to take in an unlimited number of Ukrainian people under a newly established programme that grants Ukrainian nationals temporary, three-year visas while waiving typical requirements such as fees and language assessments (Canada, 2022). The Canada-Ukraine Authorization for Emergency

Travel (CUAET) webpage states that Ukrainian nationals will not be classified as refugees, with the expectation that they will return home at the end of the three years period or apply for permanent residency (Canada, 2022). This response contrasts sharply with previous government responses to the Syrian crisis in 2015 and, most recently, the Afghanistan crisis, suggesting that the government perceives Ukrainian refugees as both less of a threat and less of a drain on resources than refugees from other regions.

A recent Ipsos study (Jones & Sethi, 2022) indicates that the attitudes of the Canadian population towards refugees may reflect these government actions. The study found that Canadian acceptance of refugees depends significantly on their country of origin. While 64% of Canadians supported welcoming more Ukrainian refugees, that percentage dropped to 37% for Afghan refugees, 36% for Venezuelan refugees, 35% for Syrian refugees, and 33% for refugees from Myanmar or South Sudan (Jones & Sethi, 2022). Despite dominant narratives of Canada as a welcoming place for newcomers, many Canadians remain hostile towards newcomers. In 2015, 47% of polled Canadians supported the statement that "most people claiming to be refugees are not real refugees" (Walker & Zuberi, 2020). Moreover, 65% of Canadians believe that immigrants are not adopting 'Canadian' values. These responses reflect the dominant discourse that portrays refugees as deserving or undeserving based on their perceived values and cultures (Walker & Zuberi, 2020).

The binary between so-called deserving and undeserving newcomers is divided along racial lines, as evidenced by both the recent response to the Ukrainian crisis and the fact that European immigrants, with their higher acceptance rating, are less likely to be racialised and stigmatised by Canadian-born citizens (Walker & Zuberi, 2020). Race has been the most reported factor contributing to newcomers' experiences with discrimination (Walker & Zuberi). For instance, a study comparing the experiences of Russian immigrant and Sudanese refugee fathers found that although the Russian fathers experienced underemployment, they did not attribute this to discrimination and generally did not report experiencing the same discriminatory behaviour as the Sudanese fathers (Este & Tachble, 2009).

Although non-European newcomers generally report higher levels of declining health than European newcomers, ethnic identity plays a significant role in shaping the level of acceptance shown even to refugees from Europe. For centuries, the Roma people have been targets of extreme discrimination and racism throughout Europe. In the early to mid-2000s, the Canadian government and mainstream media targeted Roma refugees with exclusionary practices (Levine-Rasky et al., 2013). The portrayal of Roma refugees as "bogus" asylum-seekers was commonplace in the media, and government-level measures were initiated to limit their admission into Canada as refugees (Levine-Rasky et al., 2013). These hostile responses to Roma refugees reflected the systemic racism that has been inflicted on them by Western nations for centuries.

METHOD

Nova Scotia has long been a recipient of refugees from around the world. According to Immigration, Refugees and Citizenship Canada (IRCC), government-assisted refugees (GARs) coming to Nova Scotia are primarily resettled in Halifax. In contrast, privately sponsored refugees (PSRs) are resettled both in Halifax and in other parts of the province. Additionally, it is noteworthy that approximately half of all refugees arriving in Nova Scotia are under 18 years of age. These demographics raise critical questions about their resettlement experiences and their ability to access the services they need to navigate employment opportunities within Nova Scotia communities. Our research aimed to address the following questions:

1. What is the experience of participants with available services, particularly those leading to employment?
2. What factors are likely to increase positive long-term economic outcomes across participants?
3. Are there differences in access to programmes and services across government-assisted refugees (GAR), privately sponsored refugees (PSR), and Blended Visa Office-Referred (BVOR) Refugees?

The project applied a purposive sampling strategy to recruit YREs across their varied identities, highlighting gaps in service provision and obstacles to service use across GARs, PSRs, and BVORs. The inclusion criteria for participation were GARs, PSRs, and BVORs between the ages of 18 and 25 who arrived in Nova Scotia between 1 January 2013 and 31 December 2019. The researchers applied no exclusion criteria. One of the partners, the Immigrant Services Association of Nova Scotia (ISANS), assisted in disseminating recruitment notices to potential participants through their networks, including private sponsorship groups. The recruitment email provided an overview of the study, including the eligibility criteria, tasks participants would be asked to perform, and the research objectives. Interested participants contacted the lead researcher by email and were subsequently followed up with an introductory phone call to enable them to ask questions, seek clarifications, or express concerns directly.

The project adopted Critical Race Theory (CRT) as a framework to understand the impact of structural and personal factors specific to YREs on their resettlement, access to services, and long-term economic outcomes while recognising their voice and experiential contribution to policymaking. The research participants included 21 YREs aged between 18 and 25, who arrived in Nova Scotia between 1 January 2013 and 31 December 2019. Of the 21 youth that participated, 12 were GAR, 7 were PSR, and 2 were BVOR, with 18 participants residing in Halifax and 3 PSRs residing outside Halifax.

The Dalhousie University Research Ethics Board approved the conduct of this study. The research applied participatory, qualitative research methods, including individual interviews and focus group discussions. The first stage of the research involved individual interviews with each participant. Due to COVID-19 restrictions, the interviews were conducted online via Zoom at a convenient time for the participants and lasted

between 30 and 60 minutes. For the second stage, focus group discussions were held with a maximum of six participants in each Zoom-facilitated session, lasting between 30 and 60 minutes. The questions asked during both stages of the research were open-ended and flexible, and designed to meet the needs and comfort levels of the participants while allowing them to share their experiences. All research activities were audio-recorded with participants' permission, and the researcher obtained verbal consent from participants instead of written consent. Participants were reminded throughout their involvement that they were free to withdraw from the study at

RESULTS

The findings highlighted the challenges of overwhelming job-seeking processes, a tendency towards low-skilled jobs, the underestimation of foreign education, and discriminatory access to job opportunities. Furthermore, the study found that YREs were often questioned about their abilities, had limited input in career development programmes, and experienced exploitation in their interactions with employment and education services due to language barriers. These findings suggest the need for a comprehensive re-evaluation of programme design and service delivery to address these challenges and support the long-term goals of YREs as they settle within their communities in Nova Scotia.

a. Theme: Navigating overwhelming job-seeking processes: Most studies have focused on the workplace integration of adult newcomers in Canada, while only a few have documented the experiences of immigrant or refugee youth in the Canadian labour market (Nichols et al., 2019; Woodgate & Busolo, 2018; Zaami & Madibbo, 2021). Due to the nature of their arrival in Canada, refugees face additional challenges in finding employment compared to other groups (Zaami & Madibbo, 2021). Factors such as language barriers, racism, discrimination, limited social networks, and the undervaluing of foreign credentials can hinder refugee integration in the Canadian labour market (Wilkinson & Garcea, 2017). Therefore, the support provided by mentors, educators, sponsors, family, and friends during job searches is critical to successful integration (Msofe, 2021; Senthana et al., 2020; Woodgate & Busolo, 2018). A study participant, Azeez, shared how her social networks were instrumental in securing employment:

“It was a friend of mine who I told that I needed a job. When I applied, they never accepted me so I told him [meaning the friend]. “Could you please talk to the manager?” Then he went and told the manager that I wanted to work there, and the manager told me, “Okay meet me tomorrow at 4p.m. so I can conduct an interview, and then you can start working”. Azeez, 18-year-old, from DRC, GSR

In support, Zaami and Madibbo (2021) noted that a participant in their study secured employment only because he had attended the same university as the eventual employer. Additionally, Senthana et al. (2020) reported that the sponsors of PSRs provided valuable networking connections, which aided in their job search. Due to the close relationships with

sponsors, PSRs were better positioned to receive the community support needed to thrive economically and socially. However, GARs do not receive the same level of support from their sponsors, as agencies are not necessarily invested in assisting refugees in fostering connections, therefore placing GARs at a disadvantage.

b. Theme: Forced to lean towards low-skilled and physically demanding jobs: Studies have documented the grim reality of highly qualified refugees accepting physically demanding jobs that do not align with their expertise (Wilkinson & Garcea, 2017; Woodgate & Busolo, 2018). Before immigrating to Canada, many refugee youths were optimistic about their prospects for economic advancement in the country (Senthanar et al., 2021). In sharp contrast, many YREs have faced economic hardship due to their inability to access diverse employment opportunities.

“Uh, it was helpful at some point I would tell you, but I didn't like it... because as immigrants we have no choice but to start with such kinds of jobs in Nova Scotia, which is really, the most depressing thing in Nova Scotia. Because you cannot, they cannot train you in a field that you like. The merit you have is a long, long process. You know, so, which I felt like, like I didn't belong there.”

A cleaning job is alright, but when you do it too much, you feel like, “Okay, am I going to be doing this cleaning job for the rest of my life, or do I need to do something with my life?”. Elijah, 24 years old, from DRC, GSR

The options available to refugees are limited and may potentially lead to physical harm for those engaged in such jobs. Elijah expressed the desire for more vocationally diverse and less physically strenuous employment opportunities that would prepare him and others for a better future in Canada.

“They should provide a variety of jobs, and they should accept immigrants for employment in these types of jobs. Like most of these organisations that help immigrants, they only provide them, with their starting jobs such as cleaning, the type of jobs where you have to work really hard for you to earn a living. You know what I mean. So it's really hard. It's really, really hard. Like I dislocated my shoulder while cleaning, because it's not even like you are doing really tough stuff, you are just doing one movement on a regular basis you know. You can develop a sore muscle in any way. So, they should create more jobs and, be open, like allow immigrants to be in them”. Elijah, 24 years old, from DRC, GSR

According to Elijah, the type of employment available to refugees, significantly impacts their self-esteem, mental health, and overall well-being. This is supported by a study by Este and Tachble (2009), which found that most of their Sudanese refugee participants were exploited by their employers and subjected to abusive and arduous working conditions at the meat plant where they were employed. The underemployment and discrimination they faced in the workplace, on account of their skin colour, had a detrimental effect on their mental health.

Considering that within their cultures, Sudanese men are expected to be the breadwinners for their families, being relegated to low-paying work within a system that discounts their qualifications often left them feeling stressed, unhappy, frustrated, and “invalid.” YREs are particularly vulnerable to workplace exploitation due to their limited knowledge of employment standards in Canada (Nichols et al., 2019). Furthermore, their refugee status, the challenges associated with finding employment, and their eagerness to provide for dependent family members make refugee youth less likely to speak up when they are victims of workplace exploitation (Nichols et al., 2019).

c. Theme: Underestimating Foreign Education: For young newcomers who started their education in their home country, upon immigration to Canada, many of their academic credentials are not recognised, thereby forcing them to repeat classes or courses. The lack of recognition of their academic qualifications inevitably leads to significant delays in their career advancement compared to their Canadian counterparts, who tend to enter the job market earlier (Nichols et al., 2019).

“In the beginning, it was very hard because I didn't know how to speak English with people. I went to school, they asked me to, when I came I was sixteen years old and I finished grade 11 in Jordan. So, when I came, they didn't accept anything from what I studied, they asked me to go back and repeat all of my courses because of the language”. Jason, 19 years old, from Syria, BVOR

Jason draws a correlation between his experiences within the Canadian education system and his proficiency in the English language. Several studies have indicated that the Canadian labour market is discriminatory towards foreign qualifications (Desiderio, 2016; Stewart et al., 2014; Wilkinson & Garcea, 2017; Woodgate & Busolo, 2018). It is common practice for Canadian employers to discount foreign education and work experience, leaving well-trained and qualified refugees with no choice but to pursue low-skill or survival jobs. Similar to other studies on workforce integration, Este and Tachble (2009) found that Sudanese refugee and Russian immigrant participants were often relegated to low-skilled jobs despite possessing valuable work experience and foreign university degrees. To overcome these barriers to workforce integration, some African refugee participants in a study by Stewart et al. (2014) acquired Canadian educational qualifications. However, after doing so, they reported minimal improvement in their job prospects, suggesting that other factors may be at play.

d. Theme: Discriminatory access to job opportunities: Racism and discrimination are prevalent barriers to the employment of African immigrants in Canada (Wilkinson & Garcea, 2017). Young African immigrant residents in Calgary who participated in a study by Zaami and Madibbo (2021) recounted that hiring managers were initially keen to employ them after a telephone conversation but changed their minds once they met in person. Participants suspected that this swift change was attributable to their race, alluding to the negative perceptions about Black people held by Canadian employers. Some even reported that employers were unwilling to hire them

due to their names, which were perceived as *immigrant-sounding names*. Azeez, an 18-year-old YRE from the Democratic Republic of Congo (DRC), shared a similar experience:

“They didn’t accept me because they see you, as Black and they discriminate against you. Me and my friend went to apply to a store at the Shopping Centre, and they called me for an interview. The manager just looked at me in a bad way. And then we told him we did an interview, we did everything, and he said that he will call us in two weeks... Then he said no, “I can’t accept you, we cannot accept you. We don’t like Black people working here. And first of all, you are not wearing...because at the Shopping Center you have to wear clothes like a mini skirt and look very nice” ...We just left there, we just went inside and said thank you”.

The experiences of this youth occurred on multiple levels, with the perpetrator apparently unconcerned about how they were perceived and the effect of their behaviour on the young victims. Despite completing the employment process, the manager was indifferent to whether they met the requirements because, first, he disliked Black people, and second, he disapproved of their appearance or dress style, which he assumed would not attract customers to their store. Additionally, the same participant shared being denied access to managers at multiple stores and finding her résumé visibly discarded in the rubbish bin.

“So, when I went to XX, someone was standing near the cashier. I gave the cashier my résumé, and then she threw it in the garbage. Every day, I went there to talk to the manager. “You are not the manager. Where is the manager?” But they lied to me and told me that the manager left today for vacation. Everywhere, like even XX they used to give me a lot of excuses. Yeah. I picked one of my résumé out of the garbage. No, I did not ask them. I just...when they threw it, I just picked it up and went because he was so mean, I don’t know why”.
Azeez, 18 years old, from DRC, GSR

The earlier cited study by Este and Tachble (2009) points to racism and discrimination as significant obstacles in the search for viable employment for Sudanese fathers, specifically. The Sudanese participants in the study shared experiences of being subjected to derogatory remarks from their White employers and colleagues despite being hired. Although some of the Russian participants experienced underemployment, none of them reported facing discriminatory practices.

e. Theme: Questioning capability: Studies have documented experiences of racism at work (Este & Tachble, 2009), in schools (Guo et al., 2021), in social gatherings (Stewart et al., 2012), and towards children in daycare centres (Stewart et al., 2014). Some Canadian educators hold the baseless preconception that students of African descent are unintelligent and therefore unable to handle advanced classes that prepare them for post-secondary education, which has stifled the aspirations of many African refugees (Guo et al., 2021). Azeez recounts her experience of facing discrimination from her teacher, who constantly doubted her efforts and accused her of cheating on a school assignment.

“Yeah, the teachers used to put me down a lot, that’s why I couldn’t graduate last year. I should have graduated last year, but now I’m still in high school. So I’m graduating this year. My English teacher used to discriminate a lot...I wrote my essay in my own words, and she said “Don’t copy from the internet,” and then I wrote it well, and I passed it to her. Then she said, “No, this is not your English. This not how you write it, you went to the internet and just copied all of it.” She even took it to the guidance counsellor. But I never copied and I never do. I fight so hard that I don’t want anyone to discriminate. I cannot allow that. Because I wrote it in my own words and she gave me a zero, she never marked it...I just left her, because when you report no one is going to help you. Yes, leave it”. Azeez, 18 years old, from DRC, GSR

Accounts of educators steering refugee youth toward college and trade schools are common and often lead to low-paying career paths (Shizha et al., 2020; Schroeter & James, 2015). This trend is disheartening, as many refugee students understand the value of education and are eager to learn. Discrimination in the school system is not limited to African refugees, as Empress, a Syrian refugee, encountered a teacher who accused her of cheating based on assumptions about refugees:

“...My teacher, when she saw my mark she said, “There is a problem. How are you getting these marks?” Yeah. She spoke to the teacher, and he told her that I am letting her use a translation app. And she said, “Don’t trust her, she can cheat with the information on the translation app. That’s why she is getting high marks”. Empress, 20 years old, from Syria, GSR

According to a study conducted by Guo et al. (2021), Syrian refugee students expressed dissatisfaction with teachers who held low expectations of their capabilities. These students reported two particularly distressing situations: teachers discouraging them from seeking help when required, and a teacher who placed all Syrian refugee students at the back of the class when the school principal visited.

That’s what I used to tell him: “If you are a teacher they need to chase you out; you are not a good teacher. Why are you telling other students that they cannot do this? You are saying that going to Dalhousie is not easy?” And I told him, “Yes, we need to work hard, and we know that going to Dalhousie is not easy, but don’t put us down.”

Yeah, I used to tell the teacher. I know he used to say that with our background level, we can never be accepted to Dal. We could just go to NSCC. That’s all”. Azeez, 18 years old, from DRC, GSR

Refugee students are often more ambitious than Canadian-born students (Schroeter & James, 2015). There is no reasonable justification for teachers to deem their aspirations unattainable or for teachers to invalidate or undermine their dreams by discouraging them from pursuing higher education.

f. Theme: Negotiating input in career development programmes: Educators and service providers who work with YREs often recommend programmes they consider beneficial to them. Despite YREs' lack of interest in some programmes, they are not permitted to opt-out (Schroeter & James, 2015), which leaves YREs feeling powerless and without autonomy over their own lives.

“So, because I didn't speak English, my guidance counsellor gave me courses that I didn't really need, such as Learning Strategies. I don't know if you have heard about this class. They said that they will help you with all the homework. I didn't understand. But then, when I had questions about Maths, they couldn't help me because they said they didn't know Maths and didn't want to confuse me more. So, they didn't help me, and I asked her [meaning the guidance counsellor] if she could change my classes because I was wasting my time there. I didn't receive the help, so I didn't need to be there”. Eva, 18 years old, from Guatemala, PSR

Schroeter and James (2015) conducted a study examining the schooling experiences of Francophone African students with refugee experience in Canada. Like Eva, the participants expressed dissatisfaction with their schools for enrolling them in professional development programmes designed to equip low-performing students with employability skills. These programmes did not require further university study. Contrary to the aspirations of African students, who sought high-skilled professions requiring a university education, such programmes were perceived as a waste of time, as the classes did not offer credits towards graduation. Because their institutions prevented them from exiting these programmes, the students had to use their break times to develop skills they deemed more beneficial in the labour market. These experiences underscore the disconnect between the programmes offered in high schools and the recipients' educational goals. The placement of these students in programmes that deviated from their academic aspirations suggests an underestimation of their future goals.

“And another thing, if the student says they want to take certain courses that they need for university, they should just let the student do what they want. They force the students to take the courses that are not required for the university. It makes the student stay in High School for longer... They should let the student decide what they should take, not the guidance counsellor”.

If the available academic programmes fail to reflect the needs of YREs, student morale will likely drop, participation will decline, and dropout rates may increase.

g. Theme: Language as an excuse for mistreatment and dismissal: Language plays a pivotal role in the economic integration of refugees in Canada (Huot et al., 2018). Studies indicate that refugees who are proficient in English or French have a higher likelihood of securing employment that matches their skill sets and backgrounds, ensuring smoother resettlement processes (Wilkinson & Garcea, 2017). Conversely, refugees who are not fluent in either language may

face discrimination in both school and work settings. Sofia, a 21-year-old participant from El Salvador, narrated her experience of being subjected to ridicule in the workplace due to her limited English proficiency:

“The language was the biggest barrier I had. Yeah, the second thing was how to cope with the community, as everything was different from where I was, culture, religion, language, so yeah, everything was different, okay, when I started the work. Some people recommended me, because one woman from ISANS, before she worked in ISANS she was working in the housekeeping in this hotel...When I started work, everything is good, because ...the people were very good, very nice persons, except the manager. When I speak with them, she says: ‘I don't understand Sofia’ “And when I said, sorry, my English is not very good, I am only level three, I try to understand you, please can you repeat that or speak more slowly? She just laughed and said, “This is not my problem.” “Yeah, and I saw many, many problems. Because some people give you, like, tips. She said, “These tips are not for you; they are for me”. Sofia, 21 years old, El Salvador, GSR

Sofia's experience with her manager was highly frustrating. It demonstrated exploitation behaviour, and a lack of empathy regarding her limited understanding of workplace expectations and practices. These encounters forced Sofia to seek alternative job opportunities. The manager's ridicule of her English skills, rather than encouragement, underscores the importance of employing more educators, managers, and supervisors with refugee or immigrant backgrounds in schools and agencies. Such individuals are better positioned to understand and support the needs of YREs in these settings.

Conclusion

Resettlement services provided to YREs, and their family members should include programmes that facilitate their holistic adjustment. This is achieved by soliciting and adopting their perspectives on effective resettlement strategies, particularly those that support their employment goals. These insights, drawn directly from individuals with lived experiences, should inform programme and policy development at the school, community, home, and social levels.

As documented in other studies, education plays a crucial role in the aspirations of many YREs to improve their employability. Consequently, educators should act as supportive facilitators rather than obstacles to the success of YREs within the Canadian education system.

“Yeah, I had some people at the school, like people at the YMCA that supported me. There was a teacher, she speaks Arabic, an English teacher, and a French teacher, that used to speak a little bit of Arabic. So, they helped me as, like, a regular student”. Empress, 20 years old, Syria, GSR

A participant in Msofe's (2021) study attributed their effective resettlement to school mentorship provided by their guidance

counsellor, who connected them with other students who were once newcomers to Canada. Similarly, Stewart et al. (2012) found that peer mentors with shared refugee experiences were effective in offering actionable advice on addressing workplace challenges, such as discrimination and receiving lower pay than their colleagues. Moreover, many young participants preferred to receive resettlement advice from their peers rather than from older facilitators whom they felt were “preaching” to them (Francis & Yan, 2016).

In their countries of origin, many refugees typically rely on extended family, neighbours, friends, and the broader community for support in various areas of life (Woodgate & Busolo, 2021). However, Canada presents a more individualistic culture, where newcomers often struggle to find and establish connections in their communities (Behnia, 2007; Woodgate & Busolo, 2021). Jana shared her experience of receiving community support alongside her family.

“... but I am so thankful and my family is so thankful that we had amazing people who helped us, you know like the church or other organisations or other people who supported us as kids, as young youth at our schools and also at home to help us, you know, to become more independent and learn the language really quick and go to school and learn everything. So we become a good support for our parents because my parents are still learning English”. Jana, 19 years old, Syria, PSR

Community support contributes to the resettlement process by helping refugees build a sense of belonging and overcome challenges such as discrimination (Costigan et al., 2022) and racism in schools and agencies. Additionally, volunteering opportunities can serve as gateways to paid employment, particularly for racialised individuals (Senthanaar et al., 2020). For instance, Empress was able to secure employment through her previous volunteering experience with ISANS, a resettlement agency:

I did volunteering with ISANS, so that supported me a lot to get jobs. I did some work with events, yeah events, community events. Hospital, I did daycare, I did with dental office. Yeah, I did lots of volunteering”. Empress, 20 years old, Syria, GSR

It is essential to ensure that volunteering opportunities are accessible to all YREs, regardless of their racial, socio-economic, or educational backgrounds. Our findings revealed that resettlement agencies did not provide volunteering opportunities or encourage African participants in our study to engage in volunteering. This oversight affecting this group of YREs should be explored in future research.

Ethical approval: The Dalhousie University Research Ethics Board approved the conduct of this study.

Consent to participate: Informed consent was obtained from all the individual participants that were included in the study.

Availability of data: The qualitative data from this study are fully represented in the findings reported in the manuscript.

Competing interests: The author(s) declared no potential conflicts of interest with respect to the research, authorship, and publication of this article.

Funding: This research was supported by the Social Sciences and Humanities Research Council of Canada (SSHRC) through the Child and Youth Refugee Research Coalition (CYRRC).

Authors’ Contributions: The author has contributed to the present submission.

Acknowledgements: The Pathways for Youth with Refugee Experience in Nova Scotia (PYRENS) project is a SSHRC-CYRRC-funded research initiative. We acknowledge the input of team and advisory committee members from the Child and Youth Refugee Research Coalition (CYRRC), the Immigrant Services Association of Nova Scotia (ISANS), the Department of Labour, Skills, and Immigration (LSI), Dr. Emily Pelley, and a youth advisor. We also owe the success of this project to the strength and deep insight of the 21 youth with refugee experience (YRE) who shared their stories and experiences.

REFERENCES

- Abidi, C. B., Tastsoglou, E., Brigham, S. M., & Lange, E. (2013). Refugee Claimant Service Providers: Negotiating Shifting Policies, Practices and Perceptions in Atlantic Canada. *The Atlantic Metropolis Centre’s Working Paper Series*, 50.
- Abrams, L. S., & Moio, J. A. (2009). Critical Race Theory and the Cultural Competence Dilemma in Social Work Education. *Journal of Social Work Education*, 45(2), 245–261. <https://doi.org/10.5175/JSWE.2009.200700109>
- Akkaymak, G. (2017). A Bourdieuan analysis of job search experiences of immigrants in Canada. *Journal of International Migration and Integration*, 18(2), 657–674. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12134-016-0490-0>
- Allain, K. A., Crath, R., & Çalışkan, G. (2020). Speaking welcome: A discursive analysis of an immigrant mentorship event in Atlantic Canada. *Ethnicities*, 20(6), 1197–1217. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1468796819833398>
- Baker, J. (2021). Just Kids? Peer Racism in a Predominantly White City. *Refuge: Canada’s Journal on Refugees*, 29(1), 75–85. <http://refuge.journals.yorku.ca/index.php/refuge/article/view/37508>
- Beagan, B. L., Etowa, J., & Thomas-Bernard, W. (2012). “With God in our lives he gives us the strength to carry on”: African Nova Scotian women, spirituality, and racism-related stress. *Mental Health, Religion & Culture*, 15(2), 103–120. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13674676.2011.560145>
- Behnia, B. (2007). An Exploratory Study of Befriending Programs with Refugees. *Journal of Immigrant & Refugee Studies*, 5(3), 1–19. https://doi.org/10.1300/J500v05n03_01
- Bell, D. (1995). Brown v. Board of Education and the interest-convergence dilemma. In K. Crenshaw, N. Gotanda, G. Peller, & K. Thomas (Eds.), *Critical race theory: The key*

- writings that formed the movement (pp. 20–29). New Press.
- Bernard, S. W. T. (2020). When two pandemics collide. *Canadian Social Work Review/Revue Canadienne de Service Social*, 37(2), 175–184.
- Block, S., Galabuzi, G. E., & Tranjan, R. (2019). Canada's colour coded income inequality. Canadian Centre for Policy Alternatives. <https://www.policyalternatives.ca/sites/default/files/uploads/publications/National%20Office/2019/12/Canada%27s%20Colour%20Coded%20Income%20Inequality.pdf>
- Canada. (2022). Canada-Ukraine authorization for emergency travel. Immigration, Refugees and Citizenship Canada. <https://www.canada.ca/en/immigration-refugees-citizenship/news/2022/03/canada-ukraine-authorization-for-emergency-travel.html>
- Citizenship and Immigration Canada. (2015). Canada facts and figures: Immigrant overview permanent residents. Research and Evaluation Branch: Citizenship and Immigration Canada. https://publications.gc.ca/collections/collection_2015/cic/Ci1-8-9-2014-eng.pdf
- Cornelissen, L., & Turcotte, M. (2020). Persistent overqualification among immigrants and non-immigrants (Insights on Canadian Society, 75-006-X). Statistics Canada. <https://www150.statcan.gc.ca/n1/pub/75-006-x/2020001/article/00004-eng.htm>
- Costigan, C. L., Taknint, J. T., Mudryk, E., & al Qudayri, B. (2022). Building community: Connecting refugee and Canadian families. *Cultural Diversity and Ethnic Minority Psychology*, 28(3), 338–348. <https://doi.org/10.1037/cdp0000428>
- Delgado, R., & Stefancic, J. (2017). *Critical Race Theory: An Introduction* (3rd ed.). NYU Press.
- Desiderio, M. V. (2016). Integrating Refugees into Host Country Labor Markets: Challenges and Policy Options. Transatlantic Council on Migration. <https://www.migrationpolicy.org/sites/default/files/publications/TCM-Asylum-Desiderio-FINAL.pdf>
- Edge, S., & Newbold, B. (2013). Discrimination and the health of immigrants and refugees: Exploring Canada's evidence base and directions for future research in newcomer receiving countries. *Journal of Immigrant and Minority Health*, 15(1), 141–148. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10903-012-9640-4>
- Este, D. C., & Tachble, A. A. (2009). The perceptions and experiences of Russian immigrant and Sudanese refugee men as fathers in an urban center in Canada. *The ANNALS of the American Academy of Political and Social Science*, 624(1), 139–155. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0002716209334470>
- Etowa, J. B., Beagan, B. L., Eghan, F., & Bernard, W. T. (2017). “You feel you have to be made of steel”: The strong Black woman, health, and well-being in Nova Scotia. *Health Care for Women International*, 38(4), 379–393. <https://doi.org/10.1080/07399332.2017.1290099>
- Francis, J., & Yan, M. C. (2016). Bridging the gaps: Access to formal support services among young African immigrants and refugees in Metro Vancouver. *Canadian Ethnic Studies*, 48(1), 77–100. <https://doi.org/10.1353/ces.2016.0010>
- Grenier, G., & Xue, L. (2011). Canadian immigrants' access to a first job in their intended occupation. *Journal of International Migration and Integration*, 12(3), 275–303. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12134-010-0159-z>
- Guo-Brennan, L., & Guo-Brennan, M. (2019). Building welcoming and inclusive schools for immigrant and refugee students: Policy, framework and promising praxis. In K. Arar, J. S. Brooks, & I. Bogotch (Eds.), *Education, Immigration and Migration* (pp. 73–93). Emerald Publishing Limited. <https://doi.org/10.1108/978-1-78756-044-420191006>
- Guo, Y., Maitra, S., & Guo, S. (2021). Exploring initial school integration among Syrian refugee children. *International Migration*, 59(6), 172–185. <https://doi.org/10.1111/imig.12829>
- Hamilton-Hinch, B. (2015). Surviving the impact of the experience of racism on health and well-being: An exploration of women of African ancestry living in Nova Scotia [Unpublished doctoral dissertation]. Dalhousie University. <http://hdl.handle.net/10222/73601>
- Huot, S., Cao, A., Kim, J., Shajari, M., & Zimonjic, T. (2018). The power of language: Exploring the relationship between linguistic capital and occupation for immigrants to Canada. *Journal of Occupational Science*, 27(1), 95–106. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14427591.2018.1534136>
- Immigration, Refugees and Citizenship Canada (IRCC). (2016). Evaluation of the Resettlement Programs (GAR, PSR, BVOR and RAP). Ottawa: Immigration, Refugees and Citizenship Canada. <https://www.canada.ca/content/dam/ircc/migration/ircc/english/pdf/pub/resettlement.pdf>
- Jones, H., & Sethi, S. (2022). Perception vs. reality? Canadians believe they're leading the way on refugee support, but they're actually at the back of the pack. Ipsos. <https://www.ipsos.com/en-ca/news-polls/Canadians-Believe-Leading-Refugee-Support-Actually-Back-Pack>
- Kaida, L., Hou, F., & Stick, M. (2019). The long-term economic integration of resettled refugees in Canada: A comparison of privately sponsored refugees and government-assisted refugees. *Journal of Ethnic and Migration Studies*, 46(9), 1687–1708. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1369183x.2019.1623017>
- Labour, Skills and Immigration. (2022). New record for highest number of landed immigrants in a year. Province of Nova Scotia. <https://novascotia.ca/news/release/?id=20220218005>
- Levine-Rasky, C., Beaudoin, J., & St Clair, P. (2014). The exclusion of Roma claimants in Canadian refugee policy. *Patterns of Prejudice*, 48(1), 67–93. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0031322X.2013.857477>
- McCloskey, S. (2022). The war in Ukraine has revealed a hierarchy of victims. *Policy & Practice: A Development Education Review*, 34, 138–149. <https://www.developmenteducationreview.com/issue/issue-34/war-ukraine-has-revealed-hierarchy-victims>
- Moffitt, U. E., Nardon, L., & Zhang, H. (2020). Becoming Canadian: Immigrant narratives of professional attainment. *International Journal of Intercultural Relations*, 78, 84–95. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijintrel.2019.06.004>

- Msofe, J. (2021). The importance of mentorship support for African refugee students in Ontario secondary schools. *Diaspora, Indigenous, and Minority Education*, 15(1), 10–21. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15595692.2020.1795637>
- Nichols, L., Ha, B., & Tyyskä, V. (2019). Canadian immigrant youth and the education-employment nexus. *Canadian Journal of Family and Youth / Le Journal Canadien de Famille et de La Jeunesse*, 12(1), 178–199. <https://doi.org/10.29173/cjfy29497>
- Nourpanah, S. (2014). A study of the experiences of integration and settlement of Afghan government-assisted refugees in Halifax, Canada. *Refuge: Canada's Journal on Refugees*, 30(1), 57–66. <https://doi.org/10.25071/1920-7336.38603>
- Pelley, E. (2019). Canada's policy response to refugee young people from war-affected regions: The case of Halifax, Nova Scotia [Unpublished doctoral dissertation]. Dalhousie University. <http://hdl.handle.net/10222/79845>
- Pelley, E. (2022). *Finding safe harbour: Supporting integration of refugee youth*. McGill-Queen's University Press.
- Picot, G., Hou, F., & Coulombe, S. (2007). Chronic low income and low-income dynamics among recent immigrants. *Analytical Studies Branch Research Paper Series*, 2007(294). <https://www150.statcan.gc.ca/n1/pub/11f0019m/11f0019m2007294-eng.htm>
- Pottie-Sherman, Y., & Graham, N. (2021). Live, work, and stay? Geographies of immigrant receptivity in Atlantic Canada's aspiring gateways. *Geographical Review*, 111(2), 287–307. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00167428.2020.1804301>
- Sakamoto, I., Chin, M., & Young, M. (2010). 'Canadian experience,' employment challenges, and skilled immigrants: A close look through 'tacit knowledge'. *Canadian Social Work*, 12(1), 145–151. <https://hdl.handle.net/1807/94782>
- Schroeter, S., & James, C. E. (2015). "We're here because we're Black": The schooling experiences of French-speaking African-Canadian students with refugee backgrounds. *Race Ethnicity and Education*, 18(1), 20–39. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13613324.2014.885419>
- Senthanar, S., MacEachen, E., Premji, S., & Bigelow, P. (2020). Employment integration experiences of Syrian refugee women arriving through Canada's varied refugee protection programmes. *Journal of Ethnic and Migration Studies*, 47(3), 575–595. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1369183x.2020.1733945>
- Shizha, E., Abdi, A. A., Wilson-Forsberg, S., & Masakure, O. (2020). African immigrant students and postsecondary education in Canada: High school teachers and school career counsellors as gatekeepers. *Canadian Ethnic Studies*, 52(3), 67–86. <https://doi.org/10.1353/ces.2020.0025>
- Suto, M. (2009). Compromised careers: The occupational transition of immigration and resettlement. *Work*, 32(4), 417–429. <https://doi.org/10.3233/WOR-2009-0853>
- Statistics Canada. (2017). Focus on geography series, 2016 Census. Statistics Canada Catalogue no. 98-404-X2016001. Data products, 2016 Census. <https://www12.statcan.gc.ca/census-recensement/2016/as-sa/fogs-spg/Facts-pr-eng.cfm?Lang=Eng&GK=PR&GC=12&TOPIC=1>
- Stewart, M., Dennis, C. L., Kariwo, M., Kushner, K. E., Letourneau, N., Makumbe, K., Makwarimba, E., & Shizha, E. (2014). Challenges faced by refugee new parents from Africa in Canada. *Journal of Immigrant and Minority Health*, 17(4), 1146–1156. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10903-014-0062-3>
- Stewart, M., Simich, L., Shizha, E., Makumbe, K., & Makwarimba, E. (2012). Supporting African refugees in Canada: Insights from a support intervention. *Health & Social Care in the Community*, 20(5), 516–527. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2524.2012.01069.x>
- Walker, J., & Zuberi, D. (2020). School-aged Syrian refugees resettling in Canada: Mitigating the effect of pre-migration trauma and post-migration discrimination on academic achievement and psychological well-being. *Journal of International Migration and Integration*, 21(2), 397–411. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12134-019-00665-0>
- Waldron, I. R. G. (2018). *There's something in the water: Environmental racism in Indigenous and Black communities*. Fernwood Publishing.
- Wilkinson, L., & Garcea, J. (2017). The economic integration of refugees in Canada: A mixed record? Migration Policy Institute. https://www.migrationpolicy.org/sites/default/files/publications/TCM-Asylum_Canada-FINAL.pdf
- Woodgate, R. L., & Busolo, D. S. (2018). Above chaos, quest, and restitution: Narrative experiences of African immigrant youth's settlement in Canada. *BMC Public Health*, 18(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12889-018-5239-6>
- Woodgate, R. L., & Busolo, D. S. (2021). African refugee youth's experiences of navigating different cultures in Canada: A "push and pull" experience. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 18(4), 2063. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph18042063>
- Zaami, M., & Madibbo, A. (2021). "You don't sound black": African immigrant youth experiences of discrimination in the labor market in Calgary. *International Journal of Intercultural Relations*, 83, 128–138. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijintrel.2021.06.003>

How to Cite this Article

Mbakogu, I., Wielinga C. T., Odiyi, L. (2025). Systemic discrimination and racism in the school and workforce pathways of youth with refugee experience in Nova Scotia. *Journal of Social and Educational Research*, 4(2), 25-42. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17868439>

Copyright & License

This is an open-access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (CC BY 4.0).

You are free to share and adapt the material for any purpose, even commercially, provided appropriate credit is given.